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Concerning the Knowledge Graph for Electoral Studies

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Abstract: This report describes the main results from a first stage of testing of the Knowledge Graph in electoral studies that was produced in the SSHOC project. These results were fed back to the Knowledge Graph development team, resulting in adaptations and a new version of the Knowledge Graph.

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Executive Summary

This report constitutes SSHOC Deliverable 9.10, which describes the first stage of testing of the Knowledge Graph (KG) for Electoral Studies that constituted Deliverable D9.9 (*'Delivery of user-validated Knowledge Graph, and Election Studies Analytics dashboard'*). This report also links up closely with the reports of Deliverables D9.6 (*'Demarcation Report of Electoral Studies User Community'*), Deliverable 9.7 (*'Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies'*), and Deliverable D9.8 (*'User Community Involvement in the Development of a Knowledge Graph for Electoral Studies'*).

The first stage of testing of the KG involved a small group of testers and focussed in particular on the intelligibility and functionality of the user interface (UI) of the KG. This aspect is seen as an absolute precondition for productive further testing among wider groups of end-users and focusing on other aspects of the KG. The outcome of this stage of testing was the identification of issues that hampered the user-specification of searches and user-manipulation of search results. These experiences were fed back to the team responsible for programming the KG, which resulted in an upgraded version which will be subjected to further end-user testing and try-outs.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AUTNES	Austrian National Election Study
KG	Knowledge Graph
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
SWC	Semantic Web Company
UI	User Interface (of the Knowledge Graph)

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1. Introduction and purpose of this deliverable

This deliverable draws on work conducted in Work Package 9 (WP9 –*Data Communities*) of the SSHOC project, and more particularly in Task 9.3 (T9.3 –*Data Community Project Electoral Studies*). It is directly linked to four other deliverables which all derive from this Task: D9.6, D9.7, D9.8 and D9.9. The common element in all these deliverables is that they centre around one of the major aspects of the work in T9.3, which consists of piloting the development of infrastructural tools – known as Knowledge Graphs (KG), with the subject area of Electoral Studies as the substantive field of application. The four deliverables mentioned have each their own focus, as follows. D9.6¹ (*Demarcation Report of Electoral Studies User Community*) delineates the research field of electoral studies and its associated user community. This specification is used in subsequent deliverables to help detail the kinds and the scope of data to be covered by the KG, and to sketch plans for user-community involvement. D9.7² (*Design of Knowledge Graph*) establishes in detail the desired functionality of the KG, specifies data sources to be covered, and presents choices of software platform and implementation. D9.8³ (*User-community involvement plan*) sets out possibilities for user-community involvement in the testing and further development of the KG, and the possible organisation thereof. D9.9⁴ (*Delivery of user validated Knowledge Graph, and Election Studies Analytics Dashboard*) consists of the first implementation version of the KG. The current report, which constitutes D9.10 reports on the first experiences of actual use of the KG by members of its designated data community.

This report starts, in section 2 with a summary of the kinds of involvement from the user community that have been formulated as desirable in earlier deliverables, in the form of a synopsis of the report of Deliverable D9.8 (*User-community involvement plan* – see footnote 3). This section describes subsequently why the solicitation of various forms of such involvement had to be adjusted and rescheduled, with a preliminary, limited-scale functionality test of the KG as a newly envisioned stage to be conducted before a wider-scale roll-out to prospective end-users.

Section 3 describes this preliminary stage of testing of the KG and summarises its main feedback results. It emphasises that the testing included not all aspects of the KG development, but in particular the user-

¹ Van der Eijk, Cees. (2020). SSHOC D 9.6 Demarcation Report of Electoral Studies User Community. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3725823>

² Van der Eijk Cees, Kritzinger Sylvia, Partheymüller Julia, Kaltenböck Martin, Ahmeti Albin, & Karampatakis Sotirios. (2021). SSHOC D9.7 Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558309>

³ Van der Eijk, Cees (2020). D9.8 User-community involvement plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558312>

⁴ Sotirios Karampatakis, Albin Ahmeti, Martin Kaltenböck, Johann Gründl, Julia Partheymüller, & Cees van der Eijk. (2021). SSHOC D9.9 Delivery of user-validated Knowledge Graph, and Election Studies Analytics dashboard (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4700170>

experiences with the user-interface (UI) of the KG, and with tracing and manipulating information within this UI. Other aspects of end-user experiences will be tested in subsequent testing and try-out stages.

Section 4 explains how the feedback from the preliminary testing has been used to adapt the user functionality of the KG, and how further testing and user-involvement on a wider scale is envisaged.

2. User-community involvement

Deliverable D9.8 (*'User-community involvement plan'*) describes the rationale for and the different forms in which the user-community may contribute to the development of the KG in electoral studies. The rationale is obvious: to avoid that the functionality of the tool to be developed does not match needs and expectations of end-users, which would then lead to suboptimal usage in and by the user-community and obstruct further development of the KG beyond the timeline of the SSHOC project. The major aspects for which future community-involvement was specified as desirable in D9.8 involve

- The intended functionality of the KG
- Ontology development
- Classification of training materials as basis for training algorithms
- Testing
- Post-delivery development

Many of these forms of user-involvement were originally foreseen as to be taken up during a variety of academic and professional meetings, conferences, seminars, and similar events that normally occur regularly across the year. Such occurrences would provide the opportunity to present and discuss the contours within which the KG was to be developed, and later to demonstrate and provide try-out opportunities. The Covid-pandemic has severely undermined these possibilities (as already indicated in D9.8), particularly from March 2020 through the Spring of 2021. Many events that were originally foreseen as opportunities for interacting with the user-community were cancelled, postponed, or did restrict opportunities for 'tagging on' the kind of testing and feedback activities we originally had hoped to conduct. One of the consequences of this is that –to avoid more delay than unavoidable– the first implementation of the KG⁵ was produced without the degree of user-community consultation and involvement that was originally intended. To compensate for that, and to optimally plan roll-out and testing on a wider scale, it was decided to subject the first version of the KG to an internal functionality test to be conducted by those members of the KG development group who had been part of the design of the KG, but not of the actual implementation of this design in the PoolParty platform.⁶ The testers

⁵ (see Deliverable 9.9: *'Delivery of user validated Knowledge Graph, and Election Studies Analytics Dashboard'*)

⁶ In the design stage of the KG development PoolParty was chosen as the software platform in which to develop the KG (see D9.7 *'Design of Knowledge Graph'*, pp. 43-44);

involved (from the University of Vienna and the University of Nottingham) were all familiar with intended end-user functionality of the KG, thus being able to adequately test those aspects. Moreover, they were all seasoned scholars in the field of electoral studies, thus allowing them to flag up unexpected, incomplete, or incorrect substantive results when testing the KG. The focus of the testing would be the clarity and functionality of the user interface of the KG, which was considered to be a necessary condition for any productive further stages of end-user testing. Would this preliminary test lead to a conclusion of satisfactory end-user functionality, a wider roll-out in the intended user-community could be undertaken. Would obstacles be identified that would hamper fruitful usage and testing in a larger and less select group of end-users, then those obstacles would have to be addressed first in the form of amending the implementation of the KG in PoolParty. This small-scale testing of end-user functionality took place in March 2021, supported by several zoom video-meetings which included, in addition to the testers, also the colleagues from the Semantic Web Company (SWC) who had produced the KG implementation in the PoolParty platform. The outcome of this testing exercise is described in Section 3.

3. Results of first testing of KG end-user functionality

The intended end-user functionality of the KG had been specified in D9.7 (*'Design of Knowledge Graph'*, pp.20-21) to include in any case being an effective tool for

- *General searching*
This implies that the KG should allow highly focused searches as well as undirected explorations to obtain information on research and data about electoral participation. Moreover, such searches should be easy and quick.
- *Teaching*
The KG should facilitate the teaching preparations of lectures on electoral research in general and on electoral participation in particular. Updating of searches should be straightforward to update syllabi with the latest work in the field.
Additionally, the pilot-KG should facilitate work of students by making reading materials for seminars and lectures to be found easily in ways that connect with relevant data, and by simplifying literature and data searches for undergraduate and postgraduate theses.
- *Research*
Facilitate the identification of theoretical and empirical lacunas in existing research in an easy manner and thus will substantially contribute to new research areas and outputs.

The principal focus of the testing was the intelligibility of the user interface (UI) of the KG, and the user-friendliness of specifying searches and manipulating search results. In addition, the expertise of the

groups of testers allowed also feedback on other aspects of the KG (with the exception of the last kind of functionality mentioned above, relating to research, because that functionality is mainly dependent on the volume and coverage of ingested publications and data sources, an aspect that is at this stage not yet the focus of evaluation).

The results from the testing can be summarised into the following broad categories (each of which was fed back in detail to the colleagues from SWC responsible for programming the KG implementation in the form of the specific instances where they were applicable):

- *Suggestions for improvements in appearance*
These relate mostly to minor matters such as inconsistencies in capitalisation and labelling (e.g., inconsistent use of terms ‘publication’ and ‘resource’, which is confusing as the first is a subcategory of the second); unnecessary clutter from duplication of results (e.g., abstracts of publications and datasets being provided twice, under the headings of, respectively, the description, and the abstract); suggestions were made for some more intuitive icons. It was also suggested to change the default view from ‘all collapsed’ to ‘all expanded’, as the former was found to be confusing. Some of the visualisations (graphs) would benefit from being rotated, and from displayed differently so that relevant labels would be readable. Suggestions were also provided for rearranging facets and subcategories in a manner that was felt would be more intuitive. For the same reason it was proposed to make the ‘tree’ view the default for facets.
- *Absence of functions that would be helpful*
These relate to such matters as whether elements in the search function are clickable or not (where clicking on them has context-specific results, such as including the element in question in the filtering of facet values when searching; or when clicking on results, to bring up details of the publication or dataset in question). Also including user-selectable ordering criteria for results would make it easier for searches to flow along the user’s logic of thinking.
- *Unhelpful ordering of results (including in visualised results by means of graphs)*
The first version of the KG presented search results (i.e., publications and/or datasets) in alphabetical order, which was generally experienced as unhelpful. Ideally, it should be possible to choose between different substantively relevant ordering principles, including year, or most cited, while alphabetical ordering was considered to be mainly (but not exclusively) useful for ordering authors. In cases where the search focuses on publication year, the results should not be ordered by number of search results, but by year.
- *Incomplete extraction of information*
Rather than extracting only the abstract and the full text from publications, it was experienced that it would be helpful in searches to include also fields and keywords.
- *Incomplete linkages*
Countries should be linked to election studies as related concepts (e.g., AUTNES should be linked to Austria, etc.).

- *Problematic hierarchies*

This pertains in particular to the categories of concepts and theories; suggestions were specified how to clarify this.

All comments and suggestions deriving from the testing of the alpha version of the KG were discussed and evaluated among the entire KG development group in order to avoid contradictory or inconsistent feedback. It turned out that the experiences of the respective testers were exceedingly like each other, which suggests that any other group of testers would have flagged them up as well.

4. Concluding remarks

The observation that the experiences, comments, and suggestions from each of the testers were very much alike suggests that any other group of testers would also have flagged up these same issues. That, in turn, led to the conclusion that further testing on a wider and less select group of end-users would only be productive after the various problems and issues flagged up in this stage of testing had been addressed. Otherwise, further testing would in all likelihood not yield additional insights, but merely a confirmation of what already had been identified.

A large number of issues that were flagged up in this first stage of testing could be remedied easily by the colleagues of SWC who implemented the KG in the PoolParty platform. They started with this in March 2021 and had made good progress by the end of that month. A number of issues, however, could not be resolved immediately, because they would require work on the PoolParty platform itself, rather than on the implementation of the KG within this platform. Unfortunately, these issues included some that had been identified as most problematic by the group of testers. By September 2021, however, most of these issues had been resolved as well, allowing a productive next stage of larger-scale roll-out and further testing of the KG among the user-community. This is planned for the Fall of 2021, with some of its results to be reported in future deliverables such as D9.3 (*'Usability Evaluation Report'*) and D9.11 (*'Concluding Report on T9.3'*).

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